

Results

P1

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Procesos P1	33	0	4.727	3.095	1.000	9.000
Capacidad P1	33	0	5.545	2.386	1.000	9.000
Siglo XXI P1	33	0	5.273	2.553	1.000	9.000
Extrapolar P1	33	0	4.212	2.881	1.000	9.000
Habilidades P1	33	0	5.000	2.398	1.000	9.000
Estructura P1	33	0	5.030	2.481	1.000	9.000
Secuencial P1	33	0	5.273	2.478	1.000	9.000
Pensar P1	33	0	5.970	2.592	1.000	9.000
Resolución P1	33	0	3.970	1.944	1.000	8.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Procesos P1

Procesos P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	5	15.152	15.152	15.152
2	7	21.212	21.212	36.364
3	4	12.121	12.121	48.485
4	2	6.061	6.061	54.545
5	2	6.061	6.061	60.606
6	1	3.030	3.030	63.636
7	2	6.061	6.061	69.697
8	3	9.091	9.091	78.788
9	7	21.212	21.212	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Capacidad P1

Capacidad P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	3	9.091	9.091	12.121
3	4	12.121	12.121	24.242
4	4	12.121	12.121	36.364
5	4	12.121	12.121	48.485
6	4	12.121	12.121	60.606
7	4	12.121	12.121	72.727
8	5	15.152	15.152	87.879
9	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Siglo XXI P1

Siglo XXI P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	9.091	9.091	9.091
2	3	9.091	9.091	18.182
3	4	12.121	12.121	30.303
4	2	6.061	6.061	36.364
5	4	12.121	12.121	48.485
6	6	18.182	18.182	66.667
7	3	9.091	9.091	75.758
8	4	12.121	12.121	87.879
9	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Extrapolar P1

Extrapolar P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	9	27.273	27.273	27.273
2	3	9.091	9.091	36.364
3	2	6.061	6.061	42.424
4	7	21.212	21.212	63.636
5	2	6.061	6.061	69.697
7	5	15.152	15.152	84.848
9	5	15.152	15.152	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Habilidades P1

Habilidades P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	9.091	9.091	9.091
2	5	15.152	15.152	24.242
3	2	6.061	6.061	30.303
4	3	9.091	9.091	39.394
5	2	6.061	6.061	45.455
6	8	24.242	24.242	69.697
7	5	15.152	15.152	84.848
8	4	12.121	12.121	96.970
9	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Estructura P1

Estructura P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	6	18.182	18.182	21.212
3	5	15.152	15.152	36.364
4	2	6.061	6.061	42.424
5	5	15.152	15.152	57.576
6	4	12.121	12.121	69.697
7	2	6.061	6.061	75.758
8	5	15.152	15.152	90.909
9	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Secuencial P1

Secuencial P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	3	9.091	9.091	15.152
3	6	18.182	18.182	33.333
4	3	9.091	9.091	42.424
5	2	6.061	6.061	48.485
6	3	9.091	9.091	57.576
7	6	18.182	18.182	75.758
8	6	18.182	18.182	93.939
9	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensar P1

Pensar P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
3	2	6.061	6.061	18.182
4	2	6.061	6.061	24.242
5	5	15.152	15.152	39.394
6	4	12.121	12.121	51.515
7	5	15.152	15.152	66.667
8	4	12.121	12.121	78.788
9	7	21.212	21.212	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Resolución P1

Resolución P1	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	5	15.152	15.152	15.152
2	3	9.091	9.091	24.242
3	4	12.121	12.121	36.364
4	8	24.242	24.242	60.606
5	7	21.212	21.212	81.818
6	3	9.091	9.091	90.909
7	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
8	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P2

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Aprender P2	33	0	7.030	4.362	1.000	14.000
Innovar P2	33	0	7.939	3.605	1.000	15.000
Identificar errores P2	33	0	7.879	3.398	3.000	14.000
Descomponer P2	33	0	4.606	4.315	1.000	15.000
Aplicar la lógica P2	33	0	5.000	4.206	1.000	15.000
Generalizar P2	33	0	9.182	4.104	1.000	15.000
Organizar P2	33	0	8.000	3.674	1.000	15.000
Representar P2	33	0	10.697	3.925	2.000	15.000
Producir P2	33	0	9.758	4.280	1.000	15.000
Motivar P2	33	0	10.242	3.623	4.000	15.000
Colaborar P2	33	0	9.091	4.326	1.000	15.000
Mostrar curiosidad P2	33	0	8.879	4.037	2.000	15.000
Crear P2	33	0	7.333	3.870	1.000	14.000
Ser divergente P2	33	0	7.758	4.874	1.000	15.000
Pensar de manera crítica P2	33	0	6.606	3.733	1.000	15.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Aprender P2

Aprender P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	4	12.121	12.121	24.242
3	3	9.091	9.091	33.333
4	1	3.030	3.030	36.364
5	1	3.030	3.030	39.394
6	2	6.061	6.061	45.455
8	5	15.152	15.152	60.606
9	2	6.061	6.061	66.667
11	5	15.152	15.152	81.818
12	3	9.091	9.091	90.909
13	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
14	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Innovar P2

Innovar P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	1	3.030	3.030	6.061
3	2	6.061	6.061	12.121
4	3	9.091	9.091	21.212
5	2	6.061	6.061	27.273
6	3	9.091	9.091	36.364
7	2	6.061	6.061	42.424
8	3	9.091	9.091	51.515
9	5	15.152	15.152	66.667
10	4	12.121	12.121	78.788
11	2	6.061	6.061	84.848
12	1	3.030	3.030	87.879
13	1	3.030	3.030	90.909
14	2	6.061	6.061	96.970
15	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Identificar errores P2

Identificar errores P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
3	5	15.152	15.152	15.152
4	2	6.061	6.061	21.212
5	2	6.061	6.061	27.273
6	3	9.091	9.091	36.364
7	3	9.091	9.091	45.455
8	5	15.152	15.152	60.606
9	2	6.061	6.061	66.667
10	2	6.061	6.061	72.727
11	3	9.091	9.091	81.818
12	2	6.061	6.061	87.879
13	3	9.091	9.091	96.970
14	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Descomponer P2

Descomponer P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	10	30.303	30.303	30.303
2	7	21.212	21.212	51.515
3	1	3.030	3.030	54.545
4	2	6.061	6.061	60.606
5	2	6.061	6.061	66.667
6	2	6.061	6.061	72.727
7	3	9.091	9.091	81.818
9	1	3.030	3.030	84.848
10	1	3.030	3.030	87.879
11	1	3.030	3.030	90.909
14	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
15	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Aplicar la lógica P2

Aplicar la lógica P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	7	21.212	21.212	21.212
2	9	27.273	27.273	48.485
3	1	3.030	3.030	51.515
4	1	3.030	3.030	54.545
5	3	9.091	9.091	63.636
7	3	9.091	9.091	72.727
8	2	6.061	6.061	78.788
9	2	6.061	6.061	84.848
10	1	3.030	3.030	87.879
11	1	3.030	3.030	90.909
13	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
14	1	3.030	3.030	96.970
15	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Generalizar P2

Generalizar P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	1	3.030	3.030	6.061
4	2	6.061	6.061	12.121
5	2	6.061	6.061	18.182
6	4	12.121	12.121	30.303
7	4	12.121	12.121	42.424
8	2	6.061	6.061	48.485
9	1	3.030	3.030	51.515
10	3	9.091	9.091	60.606
11	2	6.061	6.061	66.667
12	2	6.061	6.061	72.727
13	2	6.061	6.061	78.788
14	2	6.061	6.061	84.848
15	5	15.152	15.152	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Organizar P2

Organizar P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	1	3.030	3.030	6.061
3	1	3.030	3.030	9.091
4	4	12.121	12.121	21.212
5	5	15.152	15.152	36.364
6	1	3.030	3.030	39.394
7	2	6.061	6.061	45.455
9	4	12.121	12.121	57.576
10	4	12.121	12.121	69.697
11	5	15.152	15.152	84.848
12	2	6.061	6.061	90.909
13	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
14	1	3.030	3.030	96.970
15	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Representar P2

Representar P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
2	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
3	2	6.061	6.061	9.091
4	1	3.030	3.030	12.121
5	1	3.030	3.030	15.152
6	1	3.030	3.030	18.182
7	2	6.061	6.061	24.242
9	3	9.091	9.091	33.333
11	3	9.091	9.091	42.424
12	3	9.091	9.091	51.515
13	7	21.212	21.212	72.727
14	6	18.182	18.182	90.909
15	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Producir P2

Producir P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	2	6.061	6.061	9.091
3	2	6.061	6.061	15.152
4	1	3.030	3.030	18.182
6	2	6.061	6.061	24.242
7	1	3.030	3.030	27.273
8	3	9.091	9.091	36.364
9	1	3.030	3.030	39.394
10	1	3.030	3.030	42.424
11	3	9.091	9.091	51.515
12	5	15.152	15.152	66.667
13	5	15.152	15.152	81.818
14	3	9.091	9.091	90.909
15	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Motivar P2

Motivar P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
4	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
5	3	9.091	9.091	15.152
6	3	9.091	9.091	24.242
7	1	3.030	3.030	27.273
8	1	3.030	3.030	30.303
9	2	6.061	6.061	36.364
10	5	15.152	15.152	51.515
11	1	3.030	3.030	54.545
12	5	15.152	15.152	69.697
13	2	6.061	6.061	75.758
14	3	9.091	9.091	84.848
15	5	15.152	15.152	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Colaborar P2

Colaborar P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	1	3.030	3.030	6.061
3	3	9.091	9.091	15.152
4	3	9.091	9.091	24.242
5	1	3.030	3.030	27.273
6	1	3.030	3.030	30.303
7	2	6.061	6.061	36.364
8	1	3.030	3.030	39.394
9	1	3.030	3.030	42.424
10	4	12.121	12.121	54.545
11	4	12.121	12.121	66.667
12	2	6.061	6.061	72.727
13	3	9.091	9.091	81.818
14	3	9.091	9.091	90.909
15	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Mostrar curiosidad P2

Mostrar curiosidad P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
2	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
3	3	9.091	9.091	12.121
4	1	3.030	3.030	15.152
5	4	12.121	12.121	27.273
6	2	6.061	6.061	33.333
7	1	3.030	3.030	36.364
8	3	9.091	9.091	45.455
9	4	12.121	12.121	57.576
10	3	9.091	9.091	66.667
11	1	3.030	3.030	69.697
12	2	6.061	6.061	75.758
13	2	6.061	6.061	81.818
14	2	6.061	6.061	87.879
15	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Crear P2

Crear P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	1	3.030	3.030	9.091
3	2	6.061	6.061	15.152
4	4	12.121	12.121	27.273
5	4	12.121	12.121	39.394
6	2	6.061	6.061	45.455
7	4	12.121	12.121	57.576
8	2	6.061	6.061	63.636
9	2	6.061	6.061	69.697
10	2	6.061	6.061	75.758
11	1	3.030	3.030	78.788
12	2	6.061	6.061	84.848
13	3	9.091	9.091	93.939
14	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Ser divergente P2

Ser divergente P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	9.091	9.091	9.091
2	3	9.091	9.091	18.182
3	3	9.091	9.091	27.273
4	2	6.061	6.061	33.333
5	1	3.030	3.030	36.364
6	4	12.121	12.121	48.485
7	2	6.061	6.061	54.545
8	1	3.030	3.030	57.576
9	1	3.030	3.030	60.606
10	2	6.061	6.061	66.667
12	3	9.091	9.091	75.758
13	1	3.030	3.030	78.788
14	4	12.121	12.121	90.909
15	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensar de manera crítica P2

Pensar de manera crítica P2	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	1	3.030	3.030	9.091
3	5	15.152	15.152	24.242
4	4	12.121	12.121	36.364
5	2	6.061	6.061	42.424
6	3	9.091	9.091	51.515
7	3	9.091	9.091	60.606
8	5	15.152	15.152	75.758
9	2	6.061	6.061	81.818
10	1	3.030	3.030	84.848
11	1	3.030	3.030	87.879
12	1	3.030	3.030	90.909
13	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
15	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Aprender a Aprender P3	33	0	2.303	1.262	1.000	5.000
Competencia Digital P3	33	0	2.667	1.493	1.000	5.000
Competencia Medio Físico P3	33	0	2.939	1.298	1.000	5.000
Competencia Autonomía P3	33	0	3.061	1.059	1.000	5.000
Competencia Social P3	33	0	4.030	1.403	1.000	5.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Aprender a Aprender P3

Aprender a Aprender P3	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	11	33.333	33.333	33.333
2	10	30.303	30.303	63.636
3	5	15.152	15.152	78.788
4	5	15.152	15.152	93.939
5	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Competencia Digital P3

Competencia Digital P3	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	10	30.303	30.303	30.303
2	7	21.212	21.212	51.515
3	6	18.182	18.182	69.697
4	4	12.121	12.121	81.818
5	6	18.182	18.182	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Competencia Medio Físico P3

Competencia Medio Físico P3	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	6	18.182	18.182	18.182
2	6	18.182	18.182	36.364
3	9	27.273	27.273	63.636
4	8	24.242	24.242	87.879
5	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Competencia Autonomía P3

Competencia Autonomía P3	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	8	24.242	24.242	30.303
3	12	36.364	36.364	66.667
4	8	24.242	24.242	90.909
5	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Competencia Social P3

Competencia Social P3	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	2	6.061	6.061	18.182
3	1	3.030	3.030	21.212
4	8	24.242	24.242	45.455
5	18	54.545	54.545	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P4

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Descomposición P4	33	0	2.939	1.676	1.000	6.000
Abstracción P4	33	0	3.121	1.431	1.000	6.000
Evaluación P4	33	0	3.939	1.499	1.000	6.000
Generalización P4	33	0	3.667	1.594	1.000	6.000
Algoritmización P4	33	0	3.455	1.787	1.000	6.000
Resiliencia P4	33	0	3.879	2.088	1.000	6.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Descomposición P4

Descomposición P4	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	9	27.273	27.273	27.273
2	6	18.182	18.182	45.455
3	7	21.212	21.212	66.667
4	2	6.061	6.061	72.727
5	7	21.212	21.212	93.939
6	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Abstracción P4

Abstracción P4	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	8	24.242	24.242	36.364
3	10	30.303	30.303	66.667
4	4	12.121	12.121	78.788
5	5	15.152	15.152	93.939
6	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Evaluación P4

Evaluación P4	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	6	18.182	18.182	24.242
3	2	6.061	6.061	30.303
4	10	30.303	30.303	60.606
5	8	24.242	24.242	84.848
6	5	15.152	15.152	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Generalización P4

Generalización P4	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	5	15.152	15.152	27.273
3	5	15.152	15.152	42.424
4	7	21.212	21.212	63.636
5	8	24.242	24.242	87.879
6	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Algoritmización P4

Algoritmización P4	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	6	18.182	18.182	18.182
2	5	15.152	15.152	33.333
3	7	21.212	21.212	54.545
4	5	15.152	15.152	69.697
5	3	9.091	9.091	78.788
6	7	21.212	21.212	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Resiliencia P4

Resiliencia P4	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	8	24.242	24.242	24.242
2	3	9.091	9.091	33.333
3	2	6.061	6.061	39.394
4	5	15.152	15.152	54.545
5	2	6.061	6.061	60.606
6	13	39.394	39.394	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Pensamiento Crítico P5	33	0	3.242	1.733	1.000	8.000
Pensamiento Lógico P5	33	0	3.515	2.464	1.000	8.000
Pensamiento Convergente P5	33	0	5.212	1.949	1.000	8.000
Pensamiento Creativo P5	33	0	2.970	2.038	1.000	8.000
Pensamiento Metacognitivo P5	33	0	5.061	1.836	1.000	8.000
Pensamiento Lateral P5	33	0	4.455	2.223	2.000	8.000
Pensamiento Iterativo P5	33	0	5.545	1.905	1.000	8.000
Pensamiento Visual P5	33	0	6.000	2.236	1.000	8.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Pensamiento Crítico P5

Pensamiento Crítico P5	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	5	15.152	15.152	15.152
2	7	21.212	21.212	36.364
3	9	27.273	27.273	63.636
4	5	15.152	15.152	78.788
5	4	12.121	12.121	90.909
6	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
7	1	3.030	3.030	96.970
8	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensamiento Lógico P5

Pensamiento Lógico P5	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	10	30.303	30.303	30.303
2	4	12.121	12.121	42.424
3	6	18.182	18.182	60.606
4	2	6.061	6.061	66.667
5	4	12.121	12.121	78.788
6	1	3.030	3.030	81.818
7	2	6.061	6.061	87.879
8	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensamiento Convergente P5

Pensamiento Convergente P5	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	2	6.061	6.061	9.091
3	3	9.091	9.091	18.182
4	6	18.182	18.182	36.364
5	7	21.212	21.212	57.576
6	5	15.152	15.152	72.727
7	3	9.091	9.091	81.818
8	6	18.182	18.182	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensamiento Creativo P5

Pensamiento Creativo P5	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	11	33.333	33.333	33.333
2	6	18.182	18.182	51.515
3	4	12.121	12.121	63.636
4	5	15.152	15.152	78.788
5	3	9.091	9.091	87.879
6	1	3.030	3.030	90.909
7	2	6.061	6.061	96.970
8	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensamiento Metacognitivo P5

Pensamiento Metacognitivo P5	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	2	6.061	6.061	12.121
3	2	6.061	6.061	18.182
4	5	15.152	15.152	33.333
5	6	18.182	18.182	51.515
6	8	24.242	24.242	75.758
7	7	21.212	21.212	96.970
8	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensamiento Lateral P5

Pensamiento Lateral P5	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
2	10	30.303	30.303	30.303
3	4	12.121	12.121	42.424
4	5	15.152	15.152	57.576
5	2	6.061	6.061	63.636
6	2	6.061	6.061	69.697
7	7	21.212	21.212	90.909
8	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensamiento Iterativo P5

Pensamiento Iterativo P5	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
3	3	9.091	9.091	15.152
4	4	12.121	12.121	27.273
5	5	15.152	15.152	42.424
6	6	18.182	18.182	60.606
7	9	27.273	27.273	87.879
8	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Pensamiento Visual P5

Pensamiento Visual P5	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	2	6.061	6.061	12.121
3	2	6.061	6.061	18.182
4	1	3.030	3.030	21.212
5	2	6.061	6.061	27.273
6	9	27.273	27.273	54.545
7	2	6.061	6.061	60.606
8	13	39.394	39.394	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P6

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Creatividad P6	33	0	4.485	3.734	1.000	12.000
Trabajo en Equipo P6	33	0	7.455	3.336	1.000	12.000
Comunicación P6	33	0	7.424	2.332	2.000	12.000
Error P6	33	0	4.061	2.936	1.000	12.000
Organización P6	33	0	4.273	2.971	1.000	11.000
Empoderamiento P6	33	0	7.576	3.545	1.000	12.000
Predicción P6	33	0	6.818	3.302	1.000	12.000
Autocrítica P6	33	0	5.333	2.723	1.000	12.000
Evaluación II P6	33	0	7.091	2.832	2.000	12.000
Liderazgo P6	33	0	8.212	3.647	1.000	12.000
Persistencia P6	33	0	7.000	3.062	1.000	12.000
Gestión de emociones P6	33	0	8.273	3.329	1.000	12.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Creatividad P6

Creatividad P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	13	39.394	39.394	39.394
2	2	6.061	6.061	45.455
3	3	9.091	9.091	54.545
5	2	6.061	6.061	60.606
6	2	6.061	6.061	66.667
7	3	9.091	9.091	75.758
8	1	3.030	3.030	78.788
9	3	9.091	9.091	87.879
10	1	3.030	3.030	90.909
11	2	6.061	6.061	96.970
12	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Trabajo en Equipo P6

Trabajo en Equipo P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
3	2	6.061	6.061	12.121
4	4	12.121	12.121	24.242
5	2	6.061	6.061	30.303
6	3	9.091	9.091	39.394
7	4	12.121	12.121	51.515
8	2	6.061	6.061	57.576
9	3	9.091	9.091	66.667
10	2	6.061	6.061	72.727
11	5	15.152	15.152	87.879
12	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Comunicación P6

Comunicación P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
2	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
5	6	18.182	18.182	21.212
6	7	21.212	21.212	42.424
7	4	12.121	12.121	54.545
8	4	12.121	12.121	66.667
9	5	15.152	15.152	81.818
10	2	6.061	6.061	87.879
11	2	6.061	6.061	93.939
12	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Error P6

Error P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	5	15.152	15.152	15.152
2	6	18.182	18.182	33.333
3	9	27.273	27.273	60.606
4	3	9.091	9.091	69.697
5	3	9.091	9.091	78.788
7	1	3.030	3.030	81.818
8	3	9.091	9.091	90.909
9	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
11	1	3.030	3.030	96.970
12	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Organización P6

Organización P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	8	24.242	24.242	36.364
3	7	21.212	21.212	57.576
4	2	6.061	6.061	63.636
5	2	6.061	6.061	69.697
6	3	9.091	9.091	78.788
7	1	3.030	3.030	81.818
8	1	3.030	3.030	84.848
9	2	6.061	6.061	90.909
10	2	6.061	6.061	96.970
11	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Empoderamiento P6

Empoderamiento P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	3	9.091	9.091	12.121
4	5	15.152	15.152	27.273
5	3	9.091	9.091	36.364
6	1	3.030	3.030	39.394
7	2	6.061	6.061	45.455
8	1	3.030	3.030	48.485
9	4	12.121	12.121	60.606
10	5	15.152	15.152	75.758
11	2	6.061	6.061	81.818
12	6	18.182	18.182	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Predicción P6

Predicción P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	9.091	9.091	9.091
2	1	3.030	3.030	12.121
3	1	3.030	3.030	15.152
4	3	9.091	9.091	24.242
5	4	12.121	12.121	36.364
6	5	15.152	15.152	51.515
7	1	3.030	3.030	54.545
8	4	12.121	12.121	66.667
9	2	6.061	6.061	72.727
10	3	9.091	9.091	81.818
11	4	12.121	12.121	93.939
12	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Autocrítica P6

Autocrítica P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	5	15.152	15.152	18.182
3	3	9.091	9.091	27.273
4	5	15.152	15.152	42.424
5	5	15.152	15.152	57.576
6	2	6.061	6.061	63.636
7	6	18.182	18.182	81.818
8	3	9.091	9.091	90.909
10	1	3.030	3.030	93.939
11	1	3.030	3.030	96.970
12	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Evaluación II P6

Evaluación II P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
2	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
3	1	3.030	3.030	9.091
4	4	12.121	12.121	21.212
5	4	12.121	12.121	33.333
6	3	9.091	9.091	42.424
7	3	9.091	9.091	51.515
8	7	21.212	21.212	72.727
9	1	3.030	3.030	75.758
10	3	9.091	9.091	84.848
11	3	9.091	9.091	93.939
12	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Liderazgo P6

Liderazgo P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	4	12.121	12.121	18.182
4	1	3.030	3.030	21.212
6	1	3.030	3.030	24.242
7	2	6.061	6.061	30.303
8	2	6.061	6.061	36.364
9	6	18.182	18.182	54.545
10	4	12.121	12.121	66.667
11	5	15.152	15.152	81.818
12	6	18.182	18.182	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Persistencia P6

Persistencia P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	1	3.030	3.030	6.061
3	3	9.091	9.091	15.152
4	4	12.121	12.121	27.273
5	2	6.061	6.061	33.333
6	4	12.121	12.121	45.455
7	3	9.091	9.091	54.545
8	2	6.061	6.061	60.606
9	4	12.121	12.121	72.727
10	4	12.121	12.121	84.848
11	4	12.121	12.121	96.970
12	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Gestión de emociones P6

Gestión de emociones P6	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
3	4	12.121	12.121	15.152
4	2	6.061	6.061	21.212
6	2	6.061	6.061	27.273
7	3	9.091	9.091	36.364
8	3	9.091	9.091	45.455
9	2	6.061	6.061	51.515
10	6	18.182	18.182	69.697
11	3	9.091	9.091	78.788
12	7	21.212	21.212	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P7

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Desarrollo integral P7	33	0	2.758	1.601	1.000	6.000
Cómo Funciona P7	33	0	4.152	1.544	1.000	6.000
Problemáticas Sociales P7	33	0	3.364	1.692	1.000	6.000
Competencias Clave P7	33	0	3.000	1.601	1.000	6.000
Motivación P7	33	0	3.182	1.911	1.000	6.000
Tecnología P7	33	0	4.545	1.227	1.000	6.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Desarrollo integral P7

Desarrollo integral P7	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	10	30.303	30.303	30.303
2	6	18.182	18.182	48.485
3	7	21.212	21.212	69.697
4	4	12.121	12.121	81.818
5	4	12.121	12.121	93.939
6	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Cómo Funciona P7

Cómo Funciona P7	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	4	12.121	12.121	18.182
3	4	12.121	12.121	30.303
4	8	24.242	24.242	54.545
5	7	21.212	21.212	75.758
6	8	24.242	24.242	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Problemáticas Sociales P7

Problemáticas Sociales P7	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	5	15.152	15.152	15.152
2	6	18.182	18.182	33.333
3	8	24.242	24.242	57.576
4	7	21.212	21.212	78.788
6	7	21.212	21.212	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Competencias Clave P7

Competencias Clave P7	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	6	18.182	18.182	18.182
2	10	30.303	30.303	48.485
3	5	15.152	15.152	63.636
4	5	15.152	15.152	78.788
5	4	12.121	12.121	90.909
6	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Motivación P7

Motivación P7	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	9	27.273	27.273	27.273
2	6	18.182	18.182	45.455
3	5	15.152	15.152	60.606
4	2	6.061	6.061	66.667
5	5	15.152	15.152	81.818
6	6	18.182	18.182	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Tecnología P7

Tecnología P7	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	1	3.030	3.030	6.061
3	4	12.121	12.121	18.182
4	7	21.212	21.212	39.394
5	13	39.394	39.394	78.788
6	7	21.212	21.212	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Programación Visual Guiado P8	33	0	4.121	1.596	1.000	6.000
Programación Visual S P8	33	0	4.000	1.820	1.000	6.000
Programación Direccional P8	33	0	2.909	1.684	1.000	6.000
Programación Direccional Tangible P8	33	0	2.909	1.444	1.000	6.000
Programación Visual Tangible P8	33	0	3.121	1.516	1.000	6.000
Programación Visual H P8	33	0	3.939	1.802	1.000	6.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Programación Visual Guiado P8

Programación Visual Guiado P8	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	2	6.061	6.061	18.182
3	3	9.091	9.091	27.273
4	7	21.212	21.212	48.485
5	11	33.333	33.333	81.818
6	6	18.182	18.182	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Programación Visual S P8

Programación Visual S P8	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	6	18.182	18.182	30.303
3	2	6.061	6.061	36.364
4	4	12.121	12.121	48.485
5	8	24.242	24.242	72.727
6	9	27.273	27.273	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Programación Direccional P8

Programación Direccional P8	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	11	33.333	33.333	33.333
2	3	9.091	9.091	42.424
3	5	15.152	15.152	57.576
4	9	27.273	27.273	84.848
5	2	6.061	6.061	90.909
6	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Programación Direccional Tangible P8

Programación Direccional Tangible P8	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	13	39.394	39.394	51.515
3	6	18.182	18.182	69.697
4	4	12.121	12.121	81.818
5	4	12.121	12.121	93.939
6	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Programación Visual Tangible P8

Programación Visual Tangible P8	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	7	21.212	21.212	21.212
2	4	12.121	12.121	33.333
3	8	24.242	24.242	57.576
4	8	24.242	24.242	81.818
5	4	12.121	12.121	93.939
6	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Programación Visual H P8

Programación Visual H P8	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	9.091	9.091	9.091
2	5	15.152	15.152	24.242
3	9	27.273	27.273	51.515
4	1	3.030	3.030	54.545
5	4	12.121	12.121	66.667
6	11	33.333	33.333	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P9

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Asignatura P9	33	0	2.636	1.113	1.000	4.000
Trasversal P9	33	0	1.667	0.990	1.000	4.000
Extra-escolares P9	33	0	3.242	1.001	1.000	4.000
Complementarios P9	33	0	2.455	0.794	1.000	4.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Asignatura P9

Asignatura P9	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	6	18.182	18.182	18.182
2	10	30.303	30.303	48.485
3	7	21.212	21.212	69.697
4	10	30.303	30.303	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Trasversal P9

Trasversal P9	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	19	57.576	57.576	57.576
2	10	30.303	30.303	87.879
4	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Extra-escolares P9

Extra-escolares P9	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	1	3.030	3.030	15.152
3	11	33.333	33.333	48.485
4	17	51.515	51.515	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Complementarios P9

Complementarios P9	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	12	36.364	36.364	48.485
3	15	45.455	45.455	93.939
4	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P10

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Moda P10	33	0	2.576	1.200	1.000	4.000
Agentes Externos P10	33	0	2.909	1.071	1.000	4.000
Informática P10	33	0	1.939	0.966	1.000	4.000
Nativo Digital P10	33	0	2.576	1.062	1.000	4.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Moda P10

Moda P10	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	9	27.273	27.273	27.273
2	6	18.182	18.182	45.455
3	8	24.242	24.242	69.697
4	10	30.303	30.303	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Agentes Externos P10

Agentes Externos P10	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	8	24.242	24.242	36.364
3	8	24.242	24.242	60.606
4	13	39.394	39.394	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Informática P10

Informática P10	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	13	39.394	39.394	39.394
2	12	36.364	36.364	75.758
3	5	15.152	15.152	90.909
4	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Nativo Digital P10

Nativo Digital P10	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	7	21.212	21.212	21.212
2	7	21.212	21.212	42.424
3	12	36.364	36.364	78.788
4	7	21.212	21.212	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P11

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Resultados Prácticos P11	33	0	3.485	1.460	1.000	5.000
Edad P11	33	0	3.758	1.324	1.000	5.000
Disparidad P11	33	0	3.182	1.334	1.000	5.000
N Motivación P11	33	0	2.333	1.109	1.000	5.000
Inseguridad P11	33	0	2.242	1.226	1.000	5.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Resultados Prácticos P11

Resultados Prácticos P11	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	5	15.152	15.152	15.152
2	4	12.121	12.121	27.273
3	5	15.152	15.152	42.424
4	8	24.242	24.242	66.667
5	11	33.333	33.333	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Edad P11

Edad P11	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	5	15.152	15.152	21.212
3	6	18.182	18.182	39.394
4	6	18.182	18.182	57.576
5	14	42.424	42.424	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Disparidad P11

Disparidad P11	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	6	18.182	18.182	18.182
2	3	9.091	9.091	27.273
3	8	24.242	24.242	51.515
4	11	33.333	33.333	84.848
5	5	15.152	15.152	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for N Motivación P11

N Motivación P11	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	9	27.273	27.273	27.273
2	10	30.303	30.303	57.576
3	9	27.273	27.273	84.848
4	4	12.121	12.121	96.970
5	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Inseguridad P11

Inseguridad P11	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	11	33.333	33.333	33.333
2	11	33.333	33.333	66.667
3	5	15.152	15.152	81.818
4	4	12.121	12.121	93.939
5	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P12

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Formación Inicial P12	33	0	2.788	1.850	1.000	8.000
Flexibilidad P12	33	0	4.424	2.463	1.000	8.000
Burocracia P12	33	0	4.727	2.268	1.000	8.000
Dotación Tecnológica P12	33	0	5.242	1.786	1.000	8.000
Calidad Formadores P12	33	0	4.909	2.283	1.000	8.000
Difusión Experiencias P12	33	0	5.333	2.245	1.000	8.000
Tiempo P12	33	0	4.455	2.306	1.000	8.000
A Administración P12	33	0	4.121	2.288	1.000	8.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Formación Inicial P12

Formación Inicial P12	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	11	33.333	33.333	33.333
2	7	21.212	21.212	54.545
3	4	12.121	12.121	66.667
4	5	15.152	15.152	81.818
5	3	9.091	9.091	90.909
6	2	6.061	6.061	96.970
8	1	3.030	3.030	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Flexibilidad P12

Flexibilidad P12	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	12.121	12.121	12.121
2	6	18.182	18.182	30.303
3	5	15.152	15.152	45.455
4	2	6.061	6.061	51.515
5	3	9.091	9.091	60.606
6	4	12.121	12.121	72.727
7	4	12.121	12.121	84.848
8	5	15.152	15.152	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Burocracia P12

Burocracia P12	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	9.091	9.091	9.091
2	5	15.152	15.152	24.242
3	4	12.121	12.121	36.364
4	2	6.061	6.061	42.424
5	3	9.091	9.091	51.515
6	6	18.182	18.182	69.697
7	8	24.242	24.242	93.939
8	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Dotación Tecnológica P12

Dotación Tecnológica P12	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
3	5	15.152	15.152	18.182
4	7	21.212	21.212	39.394
5	4	12.121	12.121	51.515
6	6	18.182	18.182	69.697
7	7	21.212	21.212	90.909
8	3	9.091	9.091	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Calidad Formadores P12

Calidad Formadores P12	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	3	9.091	9.091	15.152
3	5	15.152	15.152	30.303
4	6	18.182	18.182	48.485
5	5	15.152	15.152	63.636
6	2	6.061	6.061	69.697
7	2	6.061	6.061	75.758
8	8	24.242	24.242	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Difusión Experiencias P12

Difusión Experiencias P12	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	9.091	9.091	9.091
2	3	9.091	9.091	18.182
3	2	6.061	6.061	24.242
4	2	6.061	6.061	30.303
5	2	6.061	6.061	36.364
6	8	24.242	24.242	60.606
7	9	27.273	27.273	87.879
8	4	12.121	12.121	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Tiempo P12

Tiempo P12	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	2	6.061	6.061	6.061
2	8	24.242	24.242	30.303
3	3	9.091	9.091	39.394
4	4	12.121	12.121	51.515
5	5	15.152	15.152	66.667
6	3	9.091	9.091	75.758
7	3	9.091	9.091	84.848
8	5	15.152	15.152	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for A Administración P12

A Administración P12	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	7	21.212	21.212	21.212
2	1	3.030	3.030	24.242
3	5	15.152	15.152	39.394
4	5	15.152	15.152	54.545
5	8	24.242	24.242	78.788
6	2	6.061	6.061	84.848
8	5	15.152	15.152	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

P13

Descriptive Statistics

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Administración E P13	33	0	2.879	1.576	1.000	5.000
Formación Docente P13	33	0	2.394	1.298	1.000	5.000
Metodología P13	33	0	2.727	1.069	1.000	5.000
Ratio P13	33	0	3.576	1.659	1.000	5.000
Recursos P13	33	0	3.424	1.119	1.000	5.000

Frequency Tables

Frequencies for Administración E P13

Administración E P13	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	11	33.333	33.333	33.333
2	3	9.091	9.091	42.424
3	4	12.121	12.121	54.545
4	9	27.273	27.273	81.818
5	6	18.182	18.182	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Formación Docente P13

Formación Docente P13	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	12	36.364	36.364	36.364
2	5	15.152	15.152	51.515
3	9	27.273	27.273	78.788
4	5	15.152	15.152	93.939
5	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Metodología P13

Metodología P13	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	3	9.091	9.091	9.091
2	13	39.394	39.394	48.485
3	9	27.273	27.273	75.758
4	6	18.182	18.182	93.939
5	2	6.061	6.061	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Ratio P13

Ratio P13	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	6	18.182	18.182	18.182
2	5	15.152	15.152	33.333
3	3	9.091	9.091	42.424
4	2	6.061	6.061	48.485
5	17	51.515	51.515	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		

Frequencies for Recursos P13

Recursos P13	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	3.030	3.030	3.030
2	7	21.212	21.212	24.242
3	8	24.242	24.242	48.485
4	11	33.333	33.333	81.818
5	6	18.182	18.182	100.000
Missing	0	0.000		
Total	33	100.000		